

How will the EU's Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism affect the Cost Structure and Pricing Strategies of India's Aluminum Exports?

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ABSTRACT

The European Union's Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) mandates that EU importers declare carbon emissions embedded in goods, particularly from nations with less stringent carbon regulations. India, the EU's largest trading partner, has a largely carbon-intensive economy, with its industrial base almost entirely reliant on fossil fuels (European Commission, 2023). The CBAM will significantly affect international trade as Indian exports of high-emission goods are poised to face carbon-related tariffs, reducing their overall competitiveness in the EU market. This study examines the CBAM's impact on India's aluminum exports to the EU and explores adaptive strategies to mitigate its vulnerability to CBAM-induced trade challenges. The research analyzes trade volume data in tonnes to maintain an accurate focus on trade flow patterns, eliminating price-related distortions. The study incorporates stakeholder insights and analyzes trade data from the International TradeMap, focusing on India's exports to the European Union, the rest of the world, and Japan (a non-EU country). It evaluates the direct implications of the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism and recommends policies to balance India's decarbonization efforts with the need to maintain trade competitiveness.

Keywords: Exports, Carbon-intensive, Tariffs, Pricing, Aluminium

1. INTRODUCTION

Under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the 2015 Paris Agreement sought to limit global warming to less than 2°C (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change [UNFCCC], 2015). Still, voluntary pledges and widespread commitments made through Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) are insufficient to accomplish our required emission reductions (United Nations Environment Programme [UNEP], 2022). The importance of taking further action to meet global climate targets was underlined by the United Nations (2022).

In 2021, the European Commission proposed the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), a major climate policy initiative aimed at reducing carbon leakage and promoting global decarbonization (European Commission, 2021a). CBAM imposes levies on imported goods based on their carbon footprint and is designed to ensure that foreign producers meet the same emissions standards as EU industries (European Commission, 2021b). Starting in 2026, EU importers will be required to pay a

“carbon tax” on goods with high greenhouse gas (GHG) emission intensity, particularly targeting energy-intensive industries such as steel and aluminum (European Parliament, 2023).

India is the world’s 2nd largest producer of aluminum, which in turn is almost entirely reliant on coal-powered energy. The country produces 4.1 million metric tons of primary aluminum annually. 56% is exported, significantly to the EU market (International Aluminium Institute, 2023). The CBAM threatens this key export sector and will likely increase costs and reduce India’s competitiveness in the EU market. Several studies have examined the CBAM’s economic, legal, and environmental ramifications, highlighting the susceptibility of developing economies and the need for cleaner production methods. The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD, 2023) warns that CBAM could lead to a sharp decline in exports for countries with carbon-intensive industries, while Buylova and Nasiritousi (2023) argue that CBAM’s success will depend on careful diplomatic negotiations to prevent trade conflicts.

This study will focus on how India might prevent its decline in aluminum exports and trade altercations by adapting cost structure and pricing strategies. It will evaluate the economic implications of the CBAM and examine policy and technological solutions to mitigate its impact. It also seeks to illuminate how developing countries might manage the shift to a decarbonized economy while exploring alternative trade partnerships to sustain growth and development.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The CBAM had been evaluated through the lens of international law, climate policy, and global trade relations, with research indicating that the regulatory shift would have significant implications for developing economies reliant on energy-intensive sectors (Espa et al., 2023). Major EU exporters, including India, Russia, Turkey, and Ukraine, were expected to be among the most severely affected by the new carbon tariffs (Bellora & Fontagné, 2023). For India, in particular, CBAM had the potential to substantially alter cost structures and pricing strategies, making it imperative for carbon-intensive industries like aluminum to transition toward cleaner production methods (UNCTAD, 2023). Studies suggested that failure to adapt might have led to decreased competitiveness in the EU market, reduced export revenues, and broader economic repercussions for developing economies (Simola, 2021). The findings of this study demonstrated how EU-specific regulatory frameworks like the CBAM would introduce uncertainties and volatility into trade relationships. This was evidenced by substantial fluctuations in India’s aluminum exports to the EU, compared to more stable non-EU markets like Japan. The EU’s unilateral attempt to reduce carbon leakage through the CBAM had used trade as leverage to encourage worldwide decarbonization initiatives. Buylova and Nasiritousi (2023) stated that the CBAM might have influenced global climate governance by either encouraging cooperation or sparking trade

conflicts. International tensions could have been avoided if the design and implementation of CBAM had been carefully managed, especially in developing countries. Assisting these nations in accessing green technologies were considered critical; without appropriate diplomatic handling, the mechanism would have disrupted international trade relationships and created global tensions.

Contrarily, Tarr et al. (2023) disputed the CBAM's ability to contribute to global decarbonization. While acknowledging its significance in minimizing carbon leakage, the authors contended that climate clubs and green technology subsidies were more successful in tackling the climate crisis. They argued that CBAM might have worsened trade conflicts and economic inequities, particularly in developing countries, if there had been insufficient incentives for technological innovation.

UNCTAD (2021) focused on the CBAM with respect to international trade, CO₂ emissions, and employment. The findings showed that the CBAM might have vastly reduced exports for nations with carbon-intensive industries. India's reliance on coal-based energy could have caused its aluminum industry to become significantly less competitive. The report suggested ancillary measures to ensure the CBAM promoted decarbonization without unduly hurting developing countries' economies. An example of this was rerouting CBAM money to help developing countries implement cleaner technology. This observation was crucial when considered in conjunction with Tarr et al. (2023), who asserted that policies like the CBAM should have provided subsidies for implementing green technology.

Another study conducted by Espa et al. (2023) explored potential conflicts over compliance with World Trade Organisation laws and international climate law. They suggested that in order to avoid trade conflicts, the EU must have enhanced the CBAM design so that it complied with global trade norms and climate goals. This argument was supported by Monjon and Quirion (2023), who examined enhancements of the CBAM structure within the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS), emphasizing the need for alignment with international carbon markets to ensure fair carbon pricing.

Simola (2021) provided a quantitative analysis using a CGE model to project the economic costs of CBAM in emerging economies. According to the data, surcharges on India's steel and aluminum industries were expected to rise by 15–35%, with aluminum shipments to the EU projected to drop by 50%. The authors contended that carbon trading schemes and increased emission transparency could have mitigated some tariffs, but the structural issues raised by CBAM remained significant.

If only these forecasts had been taken into account, the obstacles that developing countries would have faced in adapting to the CBAM might have been oversimplified. Gupta et al. (2024) conducted a sectoral analysis of the Indian aluminum and steel industries, using data from 50 Indian firms that exported to the EU. They discovered that unless rapid technological breakthroughs had been made, many industries could have faced considerable tariff increases under the CBAM. Immediate, short-term measures, including reducing Scope 1 and Scope 2 emissions, were considered crucial for continued competitiveness in the

EU market. While macroeconomic models like CGE offered useful forecasts, more detailed, sector-specific strategies were essential for mitigating the CBAM's effects on developing countries.

Mehling et al. (2024) and Best (2023) both identified the Indian carbon capture and storage sector as particularly vulnerable under the CBAM due to its reliance on coal. Their analyses emphasized the need for significant energy efficiency reforms, suggesting that aligning production processes with international emissions standards and implementing a national carbon pricing system had been key to maintaining trade competitiveness. This insight expanded on Simola's conclusions, advocating for a multifaceted approach that incorporated both national policy changes and sector-specific reforms.

Magacho et al. (2024) highlighted that CBAM disproportionately affected countries with carbon-intensive export sectors, potentially leading to revenue and job losses. Using MRIO matrices, they identified countries like Russia, China, and Turkey as highly exposed, while smaller developing economies like Mozambique and Zimbabwe were most vulnerable. They warned that a one-size-fits-all CBAM implementation risked exacerbating global inequalities and stressed the importance of tailored mitigation strategies.

Eckersley (2010) investigated the political issues that may have arisen from border adjustment measures such as carbon tariffs, emphasizing that they could have burdened developing countries with fewer environmental rules unless equal transition periods and financial help had been offered. Similar concerns were raised by Sun et al. (2022), who suggested that the CBAM would have increased GDP and welfare disparities between industrialized and developing nations. To offset these impacts, Sun et al. recommended creating an "Equitable Decarbonization Fund" to help developing nations transition to low-carbon technologies.

Lastly, Sarangi (2021) situated the CBAM in the larger context of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the UN 2030 Agenda, arguing that emerging nations may have found the related expenses unaffordable. Without adequate financial and technical support, these nations would have struggled to adopt low-carbon production methods, reducing their global competitiveness. Sarangi called for a broader policy package to ensure that the CBAM fostered global decarbonization without hindering it.

Existing research has extensively analyzed CBAM's economic, legal, and geopolitical implications, yet there is limited focus on sector-specific adaptation strategies for developing countries like India. This study uniquely examines India's aluminum industry, incorporating trade flow patterns, stakeholder insights, and alternative market strategies to bridge this critical research gap.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Aim:

This research aims to address a crucial question: *How will the European Union's Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) affect India's aluminum exports, and what strategies can mitigate its impact?*

This research has two major objectives:

1. To assess the potential economic effects of CBAM on India's aluminum export volumes and values.
2. To identify adaptation strategies that could reduce trade costs and improve competitiveness in the EU market.

3.2 Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: CBAM will lead to a significant increase in export costs for India's aluminum sector, reflected in volatile export values.

Hypothesis 2: Increased tariffs under CBAM will result in a decline in aluminum export volumes to the EU relative to the global market.

3.3 Research Design

This study adopts a unique quantitative approach, focusing on the export volume of India's aluminum to the EU, globally, and to a non-EU country (Japan) over the period from 2014 to 2023. By analyzing export volumes in tons instead of USD, the study eliminates potential distortions caused by price deflation, ensuring a clear understanding of trade flow trends. As a result, the data can be analyzed directly without requiring adjustments using price deflators or additional data cleansing steps. Japan was selected as a comparator due to its importance as a non-EU trading partner with a stable and growing trade relationship with India. Unlike the EU, Japan does not implement regulatory measures such as CBAM, offering a contrast in trade dynamics. Japan's long-standing economic ties with India are strengthened by the India-Japan Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (CEPA), implemented in August 2011 (Government of India, Ministry of Commerce & Industry, 2011). CEPA not only reduces trade barriers but also fosters a stable and growing trade relationship between the two nations (Embassy of India, Tokyo, 2024). Over the past five years, India's exports to Japan have grown at an annualized rate of 9.3%, increasing from \$9.23 billion in 2017 to \$14.4 billion in 2022 (Observatory of Economic Complexity [OEC], 2024).

3.4 Data Sources

This study utilizes export data from International TradeMap¹ to analyze India's aluminum trade, categorizing exports into three segments: (1) exports to the European Union, (2) exports to the rest of the world, and (3) exports to Japan as a non-EU benchmark. The analysis considers key external factors, including the CBAM timeline and the COVID-19 period, to contextualize trade fluctuations. CBAM was first announced in 2021, with a transitional phase beginning on 1 October 2023 and full implementation set for 2026. This transition period is critical for market adjustments and strategic anticipatory actions, and its milestones are incorporated into the study to assess their impact on trade. Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic (2020–2022) disrupted global supply chains and influenced demand, which may have led to shifts in India's aluminum trade. By isolating pandemic-induced trends, the study provides a comprehensive comparison between CBAM-related impacts and broader market fluctuations.

For data preparation, the dataset was structured into columns for Year and Export Volumes (Tons) across the EU, global markets, and Japan. Year-over-year (YoY) percentage changes were calculated using the formula: $((\text{Value Current Year} - \text{Value Last Year}) / \text{Value Last Year}) \times 100$

This allowed for a detailed assessment of trade fluctuations and trend detection. A comparative analysis between the EU and Japan was conducted to determine whether CBAM-related changes in EU trade patterns diverged from non-EU trading dynamics, providing a clearer picture of CBAM's specific impact on India's aluminum exports.

The following table presents a summary of India's aluminum export data, highlighting trade volumes across the European Union, global markets, and Japan. It includes year-over-year (YoY) percentage changes, allowing for a comparative analysis of CBAM-related trends versus broader market fluctuations, including the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and CBAM implementation milestones.

¹ LINK 1- <https://www.trademap.org/>

Table 1 - Data Summary

Data Summary Table						
Year	EU Export Volume (Tons)	YoY Change (EU Volume) %	World Export Volume (Tons)	YoY Change (World Volume) %	Japan Export Volume (Tons)	YoY Change (Japan Volume) %
2014	75,235	-	588,670	-	4,944	-
2015	33,642	-55.3	784,547	0.33	18,994	2.8
2016	95,976	1.9	970,280	0.24	31,105	0.6
2017	133,877	0.4	1,237,319	0.28	56,460	0.8
2018	236,046	0.8	1,516,463	0.23	74,770	0.3
2019	139,941	-40.7	1,962,131	0.29	79,249	0.1
2020	110,797	-20.8	2,144,802	0.09	57,768	-0.3
2021	462,243	3.2	2,667,992	0.24	106,494	0.8
2022	696,924	0.5	2,445,921	-8.30	113,346	0.1
2023	278,746	-60.0	1,957,290	-20.00	171,174	0.5

3.5 Data Analysis Methodology

To test the hypotheses, a quantitative data analysis approach was employed, focusing on trade volume fluctuations and cost implications for India’s aluminum exports. The study used trend analysis, comparative market evaluation, and statistical techniques to assess the impact of CBAM.

Trend Analysis: Year-over-year (YoY) percentage changes in export volumes were calculated to identify patterns in trade flow fluctuations. This helped determine whether CBAM-related cost increases correlated with declining exports to the EU compared to non-EU markets.

Comparative Market Evaluation: India’s aluminum exports to the EU and Japan (a non-EU market) were analyzed to assess whether changes in EU-bound exports deviated from broader market trends. This approach helped isolate CBAM-specific effects from other global trade factors.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Figure 1 - India's Export Trends to the EU (2014 - 2023)

Source: TradeMap (2024)

India's Export Trends to the EU: Figure 1 illustrates the export trends of India's aluminum to the European Union (EU) over the study period. The data reveal significant volatility over the study period, with sharp increases followed by substantial declines. Export volumes reached a peak of **696,924 tons in 2022**, marking a **50.8% year-over-year (YoY) increase from 2021**. This spike likely reflects supply chain disruptions from the COVID-19 pandemic (International Trade Centre, 2023) and anticipatory stockpiling by EU importers ahead of the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) and its associated cost implications (Bellora & Fontagné, 2023). Stockpiling behavior is a well-documented response to regulatory changes, particularly in sectors facing impending trade barriers (Mehling et al., 2022). However, in 2023, exports dropped dramatically by 60%, declining to 278,746 tons. This decline correlates with the CBAM announcement in 2021 and subsequent market adjustments implemented in 2023 (European Commission, 2023), indicating that EU importers had adjusted their purchasing strategies in response to the expected carbon tariff costs (UNCTAD, 2023).

A deeper analysis reveals that the volatility is unique to the EU market. While India's global aluminum exports have shown more consistent growth trends, EU-specific exports have been characterized by extreme fluctuations. The significant decline in 2023 aligns with projections by Simola (2021), who

estimated a **15-35% reduction in exports due to CBAM-related tariffs**. It also corresponds with Buylova and Nasiritousi's (2023) claim that CBAM introduces **uncertainties** resulting in volatile trade patterns. Interestingly, the **YoY increases in EU exports during 2021-2022** highlight stockpiling behavior, a **short-term dynamic** not sufficiently emphasized in earlier studies like those by UNCTAD (2021), which predicted broader declines for carbon-intensive exports under CBAM.

It is important to contextualize these findings within India's broader carbon narrative. Despite its reputation as a carbon-intensive economy, India has emerged as a global leader in renewable energy development, particularly in solar and wind energy (Livemint, 2023). These efforts are aligned with ambitious targets, including achieving net-zero emissions by 2070 (Press Information Bureau, 2023). This dual reality—a nation grappling with carbon intensity while transitioning towards decarbonization—adds complexity to the CBAM discourse. It raises questions about whether the mechanism sufficiently accounts for the progress of economies like India that are balancing industrial growth with aggressive climate commitments.

Comparative Analysis with Japan: A Stable Baseline

Figure 2 - Trend-Line - Exports from India to the EU and Japan for 2014 to 2023 (in Tons)

Source: TradeMap (2024)

Figure 2 illustrates India's aluminum export trends to Japan, showcasing consistent growth over the study period. India's Export volumes rose steadily from 4,944 tons in 2014 to 171,174 tons in 2023. This consistency contrasts sharply with the EU, where aluminum exports declined by 60% in 2023 following regulatory shifts linked to CBAM. The absence of similar regulatory barriers in Japan has allowed

uninterrupted trade growth, underscoring the potential of non-EU markets as stabilizing buffers against disruptions caused by EU-specific policies (International Trade Centre, 2024).

This comparative analysis highlights the importance of regulatory environments in shaping trade dynamics. While the EU market remains volatile due to policy-induced adjustments like CBAM, non-EU markets such as Japan present opportunities for consistent trade expansion, providing valuable insights for diversifying India’s export strategy. Additionally, Japan’s status as one of India's top trade partners, bolstered by frameworks like CEPA, ensures long-term economic collaboration, making it a strong baseline for comparative analysis in this study (Embassy of India, Tokyo, 2024).

Figure 3 - Global Export Trends and COVID-19 Disruptions

Source: TradeMap (2024)

In 2020, exports to the EU declined by 20.8% year-over-year (YoY), while global exports experienced a modest growth of 9.3%. Similarly, exports to Japan dropped by 27.1% YoY, largely due to supply chain disruptions and weakened demand during pandemic-induced lockdowns. The post-pandemic recovery, however, varied across regions. While global and Japanese exports rebounded steadily in 2021 and 2022, EU exports exhibited significant volatility. Notably, shipments to the EU surged by 316.9% YoY in 2021—far exceeding global growth—only to plummet by 60.0% YoY in 2023. This stark divergence suggests that EU-specific factors, particularly the anticipation of CBAM and other regulatory changes, played a crucial role in shaping the recovery trajectory.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper has analyzed trade data for India's aluminum exports to the European Union (EU) from 2014 to 2023 in the context of the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM). By contrasting trade patterns with exports to Japan, a significant non-EU trading partner, the study identifies divergent trends and how EU-specific regulations affect trade dynamics. The findings highlight an urgent need for global collaboration to address the threats posed by CBAM.

The results confirm the research hypotheses:

CBAM has significantly impacted India's aluminum exports to the EU. The data show that exports to the EU experienced volatility, with a sharp rise in 2021-2022 due to anticipatory stockpiling, followed by a steep decline of 60% in 2023 during CBAM's transitional phase. This validates the hypothesis that EU regulations create trade uncertainty for India's aluminum industry.

India's aluminum exports to Japan have remained stable, highlighting the effects of CBAM-driven volatility in EU markets. While exports to the EU fluctuated, shipments to Japan steadily increased from 4,944 tons in 2014 to 171,174 tons in 2023. This supports the hypothesis that non-EU markets offer greater trade stability for India's aluminum industry.

Discussion and Inference of Results

The findings underscore the disruptive nature of the CBAM for developing economies. While it aims to incentivize carbon reduction, its unilateral implementation places a disproportionate burden on exporters from countries like India, where industrial decarbonization remains an ongoing challenge. The volatility in India's aluminum exports to the EU suggests that CBAM has introduced trade uncertainty, affecting long-term export planning and competitiveness.

The comparison with Japan, where exports have steadily grown, highlights the relative stability of non-EU markets unaffected by CBAM-like regulations. However, India cannot immediately shift its exports from the EU to Japan or other non-EU countries unless demand in those markets is sufficient to absorb the reallocation. Instead, India must take a balanced approach—complying with CBAM through decarbonization efforts while simultaneously expanding non-EU trade relationships to hedge against regulatory risks.

The study also reveals that India has an opportunity to position itself as a global leader in sustainable aluminum production by leveraging international collaborations. By adopting advanced, energy-efficient

manufacturing technologies from leading economies like Germany and Japan, India can align its industrial processes with CBAM requirements while maintaining cost-competitiveness.

Policy Implications

Investment in Green Manufacturing: India should prioritize policies that encourage aluminum producers to adopt renewable energy sources and cleaner production methods. Establishing Renewable Energy Zones near aluminum hubs could significantly lower carbon intensity and enhance compliance with CBAM requirements.

Trade Diversification with Caution: While expanding into non-EU markets like Japan and Southeast Asia can reduce reliance on the EU, it should be approached strategically. Diversification is only viable if India faces challenges in meeting CBAM-driven EU demand. Otherwise, maintaining EU exports while adopting decarbonization strategies remains a priority.

Bilateral and Multilateral Trade Negotiations: India should engage in trade diplomacy to negotiate transitional exemptions or financial support from the EU. Advocacy for a fairer CBAM framework that considers the needs of developing economies is crucial to preventing economic imbalances.

Technology Transfer and Collaboration: Strengthening partnerships with technologically advanced economies like Germany and Japan can facilitate the adoption of low-carbon manufacturing techniques, reducing India's carbon footprint while maintaining competitiveness in global markets.

Climate Policy Coordination: Global climate policies must balance environmental sustainability with economic equity. India should push for a more inclusive global carbon regulation framework that provides developing economies with the necessary time and financial support to transition towards green manufacturing.

The CBAM presents both challenges and opportunities for India's aluminum industry. While it imposes regulatory and cost pressures, it also offers a pathway for India to modernize its industrial base and align with global sustainability goals. By strategically integrating decarbonization, trade diplomacy, and market diversification, India can enhance its position in global aluminum markets while safeguarding its economic interests. As climate policies continue to evolve, India must take a proactive stance in shaping international trade regulations to ensure they support both environmental sustainability and equitable economic growth.

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